

Fig. 2. Relationship between percentage of leaf area infested by leaffolder larvae and stomatal conductance of flag leaf.

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Effects of *Heterodera sacchari* population density on establishment and development of upland rice cv. IDSA6 under field and pot conditions

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In West Africa, the cyst nematode *Heterodera sacchari* is known to cause stunting and chlorosis of upland rice. Studies have also demonstrated its high pathogenicity on susceptible cultivars (Babatola 1983, Coyne and Plowright 1998).

We studied the effect of the nematode on rice (cv. IDSA6) development in a naturally infested field site at the West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), Côte d'Ivoire, and in 100-mL pots in the greenhouse.

In the field, rice was sown at 5 seeds hill⁻¹, spaced 25 cm apart, on 60 m² of sandy soil (10% clay, 27% silt, and 63% sand) in June 1997. The area had been sown to rice cv. IDSA6 the previous year and was known to be infested with *H. sacchari*. Because of the heterogeneity of nematode occurrence, a range of infection densities over the area was expected. Other nematodes

present were *Pratylenchus zaeae*, *Meloidogyne incognita*, *Helicotylenchus dihystera*, and *Mesocriconema tesorum*. Cyst-infested soil from rice cultures was also incorporated evenly into the soil surface. Fertilizer was applied at 60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (10:18:18) at sowing and 40 kg urea ha⁻¹ at 56 d after sowing (DAS). The experiment was maintained weed-free. At 90 DAS, 189 single hills were randomly selected and height and tiller number were recorded. Root and leaf fresh weights were measured and nematode population densities were determined from 5 g of root tissue + 100 mL of soil.

In a pot experiment replicated 10 times, seeds were sown singly into 100 mL of steam-sterilized sandy soil. Freshly hatched *H. sacchari* juveniles were inoculated in a water suspension at nine densities (see table) at sowing. Plant height was

recorded at 7 and 14 DAS and fresh root and leaf weight at 40 DAS.

In the field, *H. sacchari* reduced the growth of IDSA6. There was a negative correlation between leaf weight and *H. sacchari* juvenile population density at 90 DAS (see figure) ($r = 0.4$; $P < 0.001$). Negative correlations were also observed with root weight ($r = 0.27$; $P < 0.05$) and tiller number ($r = -0.23$; $P < 0.05$). There was no relationship between nematode population density and plant height.

In pots, very low inoculation densities appeared to have an initial stimulatory effect on plant development, but densities of 8 juveniles mL⁻¹ of soil at sowing suppressed the development of emerging seedlings. Hatching *H. sacchari* juveniles, however, emerge from their protective cysts over an extended period (Ibrahim et al 1993). Seeds germinating in the pres-

ence of cysts will therefore likely be continually exposed to invading juveniles.

The suppression of emerging seedlings and reduced leaf weight, root weight, and tiller number of susceptible upland rice in the presence of *H. sacchari* would likely affect the crop's ability to cope with additional stresses such as weeds and drought, thereby exacerbating potential losses.

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Effect of *H. sacchari* inoculation density at sowing on mean height of rice cv. IDSA6 at 7 and 14 d after sowing (DAS), and root and leaf fresh weights at 40 DAS.

Initial inoculation density seed ⁻¹	Height (mm)		Fresh weight (g)	
	7 DAS	14 DAS	Root	Leaf
0	40.6	175	0.25	0.36
10	51.0	220	0.35	0.51
20	46.9	212	0.35	0.48
40	50.4	210	0.27	0.43
80	38.9	187	0.28	0.43
100	43.8	214	0.28	0.41
200	44.2	180	0.26	0.33
400	41.0	185	0.25	0.36
800	27.9	132	0.14	0.22
LSD ($P < 0.05$)	10.7	37.8	ns	0.16
($P < 0.01$)	14.3	50.3	-	ns
($P < 0.001$)	ns	65.4	-	-

Relationship between fresh leaf weight of IDSA6 at 90 d after sowing and *H. sacchari* population density under field conditions in sandy soil.

Usefulness of blast resistance genes and their combinations in different blast-endemic locations in India

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Identification of functional blast (caused by *Pyricularia grisea*) resistance genes for a particular region is a prerequisite for their meaningful deployment. In a mini-network program, we evaluated some blast resistance genes in six blast-endemic locations

spread over five different states in India (Cuttack in Orissa, Jagadapur and Ambikapur in Madhya Pradesh, Almora in Uttar Pradesh, Jorhat in Assam, and Suttur in Karnataka). Plants were raised from seeds sown thickly (650–700 seeds m⁻²)

under Uniform Blast Nursery conditions during the 1998 wet season.

Local susceptible cultivars—Karuna (Cuttack), HR12 (Jagadapur, Ambikapur, Almora and Suttur), and Mahsuri (Jorhat)—were used in spreader rows. A single row